

Systematic Analysis of Distance Learning in Higher Education Using Story Map

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Abstract. The study in progress is concerned with mapping the situation of distance learning in higher education in the Central European region. Utilising narrative visualisation, the research aims to communicate the availability and status of distance learning in the region, allowing for better-informed strategic planning on the part of universities. The expected output of the study is a story map providing distance learning data in context, served in a reader-driven fashion.

Keywords. distance learning mapping, higher education, data storytelling, story map, interactive map

1. Introduction

In the European context, the popularity of distance learning in higher education rose significantly during recent events preventing in-person education, including the Covid-19 pandemic or martial law in Ukraine (Shlenova et al. 2023, Bidarra et al. 2024). Distance learning has proved itself as an effective method of teaching. It puts the student experience at the forefront of the process and enables cooperation between different universities for the benefit of the students.

According to the European Association of Distance Teaching Universities (2025), many universities are providing distance learning programmes all over the European area. However, no single source has been identified that would map the current state of distance education in Central Europe, which is the region of interest for the authors of the research. This research gap leads to an opportunity to create a synthesised source aggregating all universities offering distance learning in the region.

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The study aims to develop a reader-centred data product serving for decision-making in cross-university collaboration activities. As such, the goal is not merely to present the raw data on distance learning but rather to build a storytelling narrative surrounding its state and development. A story map is a suitable tool supporting the creation of such a narrative, thanks to providing an effective synthesis of geospatial data and additional logical information (Malkowski & Klenke 2020).

2. State of the research

The primary part of the story map is a thematic map that will present the availability of distance learning in Central Europe. The map is developed using a modular strategy to support the extensibility of data contents, interactivity, and overall user interface design. The map's basis is formed by a geospatial database containing selected details about distance programmes from specific universities in the Central European region.

2.1. Data collection

A set of attributes to be collected for each distance learning programme was defined to balance the information contents and usability of the map. The database attributes included general information on the university and details on the specific distance learning programmes it offers. The database schema is captured in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Schema of geodatabase and collected attributes. (Location refers to the seat of the university.)

Data was collected from official sources maintained by relevant authorities in each respective country researched (e.g., the Ministry of Education). From such sources, information conforming to the pre-defined attributes was systematically harvested. If a source failed to provide the required information, such as the accreditation details, a supplementary source was identified and used to complete the data set where available.

The country selection was motivated by the potential of cross-border cooperation between universities. The data collection process started in the first phase with institutions of higher education in the Czech Republic before proceeding to the universities in surrounding countries. The data sources covering Austria, Poland, and Slovakia were fully explored. The research on programmes in Germany was limited to the federal states neighbouring the Czech Republic, i.e. Bavaria and Saxony.

The amount of distance learning programmes identified varied significantly by country. The lowest amount, zero, was identified in Slovakia. On the other hand, higher education institutions in Poland were found to offer the highest absolute number of programmes so far, 315 in total.

2.2. Tool selection

A platform was required to support making the story map available online. Multiple software platforms were evaluated to support the objective, based on the following aspects:

- modularity,
- ease of implementation (low-code or no-code solutions preferred),
- responsiveness,
- accessibility for all target users and devices,
- acceptable cost with respect to the research budget.

The specific evaluated platforms included QGIS Cloud, Mapbox, Google Earth Engine, and ArcGIS Online. Out of the listed tools, ArcGIS Online was ultimately selected as the platform to support the implementation of the story map due to meeting all the defined criteria, including simplicity of use and widely available support. Additionally, the financial criterium was met thanks to the university providing a pre-existing license for the platform to the researchers, avoiding extra costs for the research.

Out of the variety of tools offered by ArcGIS Online¹, the Experience Builder tool was selected. The tool allows for designing interactive visualisations, as well as providing expandability of the data layers displayed.

2.3. Current state of our work

The proposed story map utilises the drill-down story approach (see *Figure 2*), which was deemed to be the most suitable narrative type for empowering users to explore the story at their own pace, while placing the map in the central part of the story map (Segel & Heer 2010).

Figure 2. Schema of drill-down story narrative approach according to Segel & Heer (2010).

The development of the story map commenced by sketching a low-fidelity paper prototype, followed by an interactive prototype created using the Figma software². The prototype begins from an overall map view, displaying the spatial distribution of universities providing distance learning programmes across the studied region. A list of distance programmes offered

¹ <https://www.arcgis.com/index.html>

² Link to the clickable Figma prototype:
https://www.figma.com/proto/TJooSirbBF8x1GG8CLBIY9/Distance_learning_map?node-id=0-1&t=3htPcGY4dhr84XCT-1

by that institution is displayed by clicking on one of the buttons representing universities. More information about specific related topics is accessible to users by clicking on a topic's name (see *Figure 3*).

Figure 3. General schema of the story map.

Following the basic prototype, the initial version of the main map visualisation was designed (see *Figure 4*). The plan of the work is to finalise the main map and create a narrative using socioeconomic analyses, such as GDP or unemployment in the specific country.

Figure 4. Preview of the main map in the Experience Builder interface.

3. Conclusion

The proposed story map design aims to communicate the state of distance learning in higher education across Central Europe. The resulting map is expected to serve as a decision-making tool, especially for universities seeking to establish mutual cooperation. It can also serve as an information platform for individuals interested in studying a distance learning programme.

To complete the work in progress, we aim to perform a second data collection phase, focused on the remaining federal states of Germany and other countries, followed by finishing the design and implementation of the story map itself. The possible future transition to a long-term data collection process, as well as visualisation of other related topics, will be discussed.

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